

Behaviour of Simple Electrodes in Potentiometric Determination of Acid-base Titrations

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On studying the galvanostatic potential of tin and cadmium electrodes in different solutions¹, these electrodes were found to possess a potential amplifying property, *i.e.*, a capacity to give rise to potential changes ~ 60 mv/pH.

In the present note a trial is reported of using these electrodes in media beyond pH 7 for titrations of strong alkali with strong and weak acids.

Procedure.—Solutions of citric, hydrochloric, sulphuric, phosphoric, and acetic acids were prepared from AnalaR reagents and checked by following the standard methods. The standard NaOH solution used was prepared and diluted according to Vogel².

The electroplated electrodes of tin and tin amalgam used were prepared after El Wakkad *et al.*¹. The electroplated cadmium electrodes were prepared according to the procedure of Blum and Hogaboom³.

FIG. 1. Titration of NaOH vs HCl and AcOH (1,0.1 and 0.01)

FIG. 2. Titration of NaOH vs HCl (1 & 0.01) and AcOH (1,0.1 & 0.01)

1. El Wakkad *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 3700; Tourky and Issa, Ph.D. thesis, 1950.
2. "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis," Longmans, Green and Co., London, 1939, p. 268.
3. "Principles of Electroplating and Electropolishing" 3rd ed., 1049, p. 315.

The potentiometric arrangement was similar to the one used previously described⁴. The indicator electrode used was the cadmium electrode, the tin electrode, or tin amalgam electrode. The reference electrode was a saturated calomel electrode which had a potential value of 0.245 V at 25°.

Figs. 1-3 show the changes in E. M. F. of the combination cadmium, tin, and tin amalgam electrodes—reference electrode in several acid-base titrations. Fig. 2 shows that the equivalence point is followed by a rise in potential due to the dissolution of tin in strong acid solutions¹. For this reason it was preferred to apply tin amalgam in these titrations since this electrode can resist such dissolution behaving mainly as an indicator electrode for hydrogen-ion concentrations even in the strong acid ranges. Thus, using the amalgamated tin electrodes makes the jump in the potential at end points comparatively smooth, especially at higher concentrations with pronounced accuracy. The electroplated tin electrode dissolves beyond 1*N* concentration of acid-base titration, decreasing the accuracy of its applications. Fig. 3 represents the amalgamated tin electrodes in acid-base titrations.

FIG. 3. Titration of NaOH vs $\sim 3 N$ -HCl, H_3PO_4 , H_2SO_4 and AcOH.

In all titrations the solutions used cover the concentration from 3 *N* to $1 \times 10^{-3} N$ in case of strong acids and 3 *N* to $10^{-2} N$ in case of weak acids at 25°. Under such condition a maximum value for $\Delta E / \Delta C$, *C* being referred to 0.1 ml acid was obtained at 100% neutralisation exactly. This confirms the view according to which these electrodes can be used as indicator electrode in acid-base titrations.

4. Salem and Hanafi, *Proc. Egypt Acad. Sci.*, 1959, 13, 3; Salem and Awad, *J. Chem. A. U. R.*, in press.